

Mean value of F. Smarandache LCM function

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. The Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $(SL(n) - S(n))^2$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords Smarandache function, Smarandache LCM function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. For example, the first few values of $S(n)$ are $S(1) = 1, S(2) = 2, S(3) = 3, S(4) = 4, S(5) = 5, S(6) = 3, S(7) = 7, S(8) = 4, S(9) = 6, S(10) = 5, S(11) = 11, S(12) = 4, \dots$. The F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. The first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1, SL(2) = 2, SL(3) = 3, SL(4) = 4, SL(5) = 5, SL(6) = 3, SL(7) = 7, SL(8) = 8, SL(9) = 9, SL(10) = 5, SL(11) = 11, SL(12) = 4, \dots$.

About the elementary properties of $S(n)$ and $SL(n)$, many authors had studied them, and obtained some interesting results, see reference [2], [3], [4] and [5]. For example, Murthy [2] proved that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$. Simultaneously, Murthy [2] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n ? \quad (1)$$

Le Maohua [3] completely solved this problem, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}, i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Dr. Xu Zhefeng [4] studied the value distribution problem of $S(n)$, and proved the following conclusion:

Let $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime factor of n , then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2\zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3 \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ denotes the Riemann zeta-function.

Lv Zhongtian [5] proved that for any fixed positive integer k any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula fixed positive integer k

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $[SL(n) - S(n)]^2$, and give an interesting mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. Let k be a fixed positive integer. Then for any real number $x > 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ be the Riemann zeta-function, c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of our theorem directly. In fact for any positive integer $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n into prime powers, then from [2] we know that

$$S(n) = \max\{S(p_1^{\alpha_1}), S(p_2^{\alpha_2}), \dots, S(p_s^{\alpha_s})\} \equiv S(p^\alpha) \quad (2)$$

and

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_s^{\alpha_s}\}. \quad (3)$$

Now we consider the summation

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = \sum_{n \in A} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 + \sum_{n \in B} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2, \quad (4)$$

where A and B denote two subsets of all positive integer in the interval $[1, x]$. A denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that $SL(n) = p^2$ for some prime p ; B denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that $SL(n) = p^\alpha$ for some prime p with $\alpha = 1$ or $\alpha \geq 3$. If

$n \in A$ and $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$, then $n = p^2 m$ with $p \nmid m$, and all $p_i^{\alpha_i} \leq p^2$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, s$. Note that $S(p_i^{\alpha_i}) \leq \alpha_i p_i$ and $\alpha_i \leq \ln n$, from the definition of $SL(n)$ and $S(n)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \in A} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 &= \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ SL(m) < p^2}} [p^2 - S(mp^2)]^2 \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ SL(m) < p^2}} (p^4 - 2p^2 S(mp^2) + S^2(mp^2)) \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ SL(m) < p^2}} p^4 + O\left(\sum_{mp^2 \leq x} p^2 \cdot p \cdot \ln x\right) + O\left(\sum_{mp^2 \leq x} p^2 \cdot \ln^2 x\right) \\
 &= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{m < p^2 \leq \frac{x}{m}} p^4 + O\left(\sum_{p^2 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p^2 < m \leq \frac{x}{p^2}} p^4\right) + O(x^2) \\
 &= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} p^4 + O\left(\sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p^2 \leq m} p^4\right) + O(x^2) \\
 &= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} p^4 + O(x^2). \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

By the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [6]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [7]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} p^4 &= \frac{x^2}{m^2} \cdot \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}\right) - \int_{\frac{3}{2}}^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} 4y^3 \cdot \pi(y) dy \\
 &= \frac{x^2}{m^2} \cdot \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}\right) - \int_{\frac{3}{2}}^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} 4y^3 \left[\sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot y}{\ln^i y} + O\left(\frac{y}{\ln^{k+1} y}\right) \right] dy \\
 &= \frac{1}{5} \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{m^{\frac{5}{2}}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{m^{\frac{5}{2}} \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the estimate $m \leq \sqrt{x}$, and all b_i are computable constants with $b_1 = 1$.

Note that $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \zeta\left(\frac{5}{2}\right)$, and $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^i m}{m^{\frac{5}{2}}}$ is convergent for all $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$. So

from (5) and (6) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n \in A} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 \\
 &= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \left[\frac{1}{5} \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{m^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{m^{\frac{5}{2}} \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right) \right] + O(x^2) \\
 &= \frac{2}{5} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{5}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $c_1 = 1$.

Now we estimate the summation in set B . For any positive integer $n \in B$. If $n \in B$ and $SL(n) = p$, then we also have $S(n) = p$. So $[SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = [p - p]^2 = 0$. If $SL(n) = p^\alpha$ with $\alpha \geq 3$, then $[SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = [p^\alpha - S(n)]^2 \leq p^{2\alpha} + \alpha^2 p^2$ and $\alpha \leq \ln n$. So we have

$$\sum_{n \in B} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 \ll \sum_{\substack{np^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 3}} (p^{2\alpha} + p^2 \ln^2 n) \ll x^2. \tag{8}$$

Combining (4), (7) and (8) we may immediately deduce the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{5}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $c_1 = 1$.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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